

An Empirical Analysis of the Impact of Digitalization on Small Business in Udupi

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ABSTRACT

The era of digitalization has guided in a new age of technological advancement, fundamentally transforming the way we live, work, and communicate. With the rapid integration of digital technologies into various aspects of our lives, society has experienced unprecedented changes, offering immense opportunities and challenges in equal measure. This research study mainly focuses on study of impact of digitalization to small business owners. This study mainly focuses on impact of digital payment, ecommerce platforms and other digital tools to small businesses. The study also focuses on the socio-economic condition of these small business owners and also their way of running business. The study facilitated the learning about research concepts in practical world and helped us in understanding various statistical tools used in research methodology and drawing conclusion using them.

Keywords: Digitalization, Small business, Digital transformation, Competitive advantage

1. INTRODUCTION:

Digitalization has become one of the most rapidly growing concepts in today's business environment. It plays a pivotal role in reducing costs and time by automating activities and providing efficient tools. Various software, applications, websites, and social media platforms significantly contribute to the growth of organizations by streamlining processes and enhancing market reach. Large firms often leverage digital technologies to manage different aspects of their operations, including production, marketing, and promotion. Digitalization not only supports organizations in accessing critical market information but also enhances their operational efficiency. However, small businesses face several constraints when it comes to adopting digitalization. These challenges include capital limitations, the educational background of business owners, lack of digital literacy, and a general resistance to business innovation. Despite these barriers, if small businesses embrace digital platforms and utilize available digital tools, they stand to gain significantly. Digitalization can foster growth, expand market reach, and increase revenue by connecting small businesses to a wider customer base at lower costs and in less time. This study focuses on small businesses in the Udupi district, aiming to understand their challenges and perspectives on digitalization. We examined both the positive and negative impacts of digital adoption on these businesses to better grasp the benefits and obstacles they experience.

2.LITERATURE REVIEW:

A literature review is an essential component of academic writing that demonstrates a comprehensive understanding of the existing literature on a specific topic within a relevant context. A critical evaluation of the material is included, distinguishing it from a literature report, making it more analytical in nature.

Arora and Rathi (2019) conducted a study aimed at analyzing the impact of digitalization on small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in India. Their objective was to determine the effect of digitalization on small businesses and identify the challenges faced by organizations due to digitalization. The study employed both analytical and descriptive approaches, utilizing primary and secondary data sources. A range of business sizes formed the study's sample. Statistical tools such as t-tests and regression analysis were used. The findings indicated that lack of awareness, expertise, and knowledge were key barriers to digitalization in small businesses. Additionally, the size of the firm played a critical role in implementing digital strategies. However, increases in sales, profitability, competitive capability, and brand awareness motivated businesses to adopt digitalization.

Shettima and Sharma (2020) explored the impact of digitalization on SMEs in Nigeria. The study utilized both primary and secondary data sources, with a survey method that included distributing questionnaires to 500 SMEs. The chi-square model was applied to evaluate the impact of digitalization. Their findings demonstrated that ICT adoption among SMEs significantly enhanced productivity and economic activities.

Molotkova, Khazanova, and Ivanova (2019) conducted a study to examine the influence of digitalization on small businesses within the broader context of the digital economy. The study employed a systems approach, structural-functional analysis, expert assessments, and content analysis of scientific literature. Through this research, the authors identified various advantages and barriers related to digitalization for small business operations.

Zhao, Havakhor, and Mandviwalla (2022) investigated the digitalization architecture of SMEs in the United States. Data was collected from the Computer Intelligence Technology Database, using both primary and secondary sources. SMEs were categorized into three groups based on employee size: micro (1-9 employees), small (10-99 employees), and medium (100-499 employees). The study found that SMEs could be classified as digital laggards, digital leaders, or digital analyzers, depending on their level of digital adoption across various domains.

Rachinger et al. (2018) explored the effect of digitalization on business models by collecting qualitative empirical data from 12 key informants across the media and automotive industries. The study examined how digitalization influenced value creation, value proposition, and value capture within organizations. The results highlighted the crucial role digitalization plays in fostering value networks and driving business model innovation.

3.RESEARCH GAP:

While the aforementioned studies explored the digitalization of small businesses in various global contexts, none focused specifically on the Udupi district. This gap in research provided an opportunity to conduct a study on the impact of digitalization on small businesses in Udupi, thereby contributing valuable insights to this under-researched area.

4. RESEARCH DESIGN:

In this study mainly we followed various steps of research procedures for the smooth flow of the activity. At first, we investigated about various socio-economic problems and found this topic. Then we referred other studies done by experts' study about the problem and to conduct research process.

5. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

- To examine the extent of digital adoption among small businesses
- To analyse the perception of small business owners about digitalization business
- To identify and analyse the factors influencing the adoption of digitalisation among small business owners
- To analyse the challenges faced by small business owners in using the digital platforms
- To suggest measures to strengthen the digitalisation of small businesses.

6. RESEARCH METHOD:

Type of research design: This is empirical research as it involves collection of data from the field. It is primary data-based study. This research work is descriptive in nature.

Sources of Data:

- Primary Data: Mainly collected through questionnaire and survey
- Secondary Data: Collected through websites like research gate and google scholar

Sampling Design:

- Sampling unit: Small business owners
- Sampling element: Small business owners of Udupi district
- Sample Size: 60
- Sampling Method: convenience sampling was used based on the availability of small business owners

Limitations of the study:

- Time constraint for the paper
- Small sample size
- Biased on the response of small business owners

7. CONCEPTUAL BACKGROUND:

Digitalization

Digitalization is the process of leveraging digital technologies to transform a business model, creating new revenue streams and value-producing opportunities. This involves integrating digital tools and systems into various aspects of a business's operations, from management and communication to production and customer service.

In today's competitive landscape, digitalization has become essential for businesses to stay relevant and thrive. It enables organizations to adapt to rapidly changing market conditions, meet customer expectations, and optimize their processes for greater efficiency and productivity.

Using digitized information, digitalization is the process of making workflows and processes easier and more efficient. Especially in today's tech-driven world, it is crucial to adopt a digital culture in order to survive and succeed.

Small business

Business which functions on a small-scale level involves less capital investment, a smaller number of workers and fewer machines to operate is known as a small business. Small scale Industries or small business are the type of industries that produces goods and services on a small scale.

These industries play an important role in the economic development of a country. The owner invests once on machinery, industries, and plants, or take is a lease or hire purchase. These industries do not invest more than one crore. Few examples of small-scale industries are paper, toothpick, pen, bakeries, candles, local chocolate, etc., industries and are mostly settled in an urban area as a separate unit.

8.DATA ANALYSIS:

Data Analysis is the process of systematically applying statistical and/or logical techniques to describe and illustrate, condense and recap, and evaluate data.

According to Shamo and Resnik (2003) various analytic procedures "provide a way of drawing inductive inferences from data and distinguishing the signal (the phenomenon of interest) from the noise (statistical fluctuations) present in the data".

In this study we used various statistical techniques to conduct research and get the conclusion. Various forms of charts were used for pictorial representation of the data. This pictorial representation will help in drawing conclusion to various questions easily.

Various statistical tools such as mean average, hypotheses testing, were performed to get better solution to the problem and to learn about the economy. Mainly we used PSPP and Microsoft excel software's to perform statistical calculations. We used statistical tools such as chi-square, mean and standard deviation to come to the conclusion.

Age group of the respondents-

Table 1: Table showing age group of respondents

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Below 30	5	8.2%	8.2%	8.2%
30-40	8	13.1%	13.1%	21.3%
40-50	20	32.8%	32.8%	54.1%
50-60	21	34.4%	34.4%	88.5%
60&Above	6	11.5%	11.5%	100.0%
Total	60	100.0%		

Source: Made through PSPP

Chart 1: Chart showing age group of respondents

Source: Made through excel

Interpretation-

As per the pie chart we can analyse that people of age group 40-50 and 50-60 are engaged more in small business that is 35% and 34% respectively. But when it comes to other age group of 60 and above only 10% of people who are engaged in small business. People who are of age group below 30 and 30-40 are less involved in small business. These calculations are mainly based on our assumptions.

Annual turnover of small business-

Table 2: Table showing annual turnover of small business

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
20000-40000	7	11.7%	11.7%	11.7%
40000-60000	20	33.3%	33.3%	45.0%
60000-80000	15	25.0%	25.0%	70.0%
100000&Above	18	30.0%	30.0%	100.0%
Total	60	100.0%		

Source: Made through PSPP

Chart 2: Chart showing age group of respondents

Source: Made through excel

Interpretation-

As per the data collected from the we interpreted it that 11.7% of the business has a annual turnover of only 20000-40000. Nearly 33% of the business has a annual turnover of 40000-60000 and it has highest frequency and nearly 25% of the company has annual turnover of 60000-80000 and 30% of the business or owners have a turnover of more than 100000.

Area of operation of the small business-

Table 3: Table showing the area of operation

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Urban	10	16.7%	16.7%	16.7%
Semi urban	15	25%	25%	41.7%
Rural	35	58.3%	58.3%	100%
Total	60	100.0%		

Chart 3: Chart showing area of operation

Source: Made through excel

Interpretation-

In this survey we mainly concentrated on rural area. As you can see in the above chart nearly 60% of the business were setup in rural areas. 25% of the business were setup in semi-urban or semi-rural areas and only 16% business were setup in urban areas. By this we can conclude that rural area will help in country development and its GDP.

Education level of the respondents-

Table 4 :Table showing the education level of the respondents

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Primary	5	8.3%	8.3%	8.3%
High School	17	28.3%	28.3%	36.7%
College	12	20.0%	20.0%	56.7%
Graduation	26	43.3%	43.3%	100.0%
Total	60	100.0%		

Source: Made through PSPP

Chart 4: Chart showing educational qualification of the respondents

Source: Made through excel

Interpretation-

Based on this we can analyse that most of the small business owners have graduation degree. Only 8% of the sample has dropped out from school. This implies that the people in current scenario have good awareness about education. In rural area also people try to get a good education nowadays.

Use of digital payment by small business owners-

Chart 5: Chart showing usage of digital payment platform by the respondents

Interpretation-

This question was asked with the intention to learn about the digital literacy of the respondents. The study showed that nearly 83% of the respondents are using digital payment platforms in their business and are adapting to changes. Only 17% of the respondents were not using the digital payment platforms.

Use of E-commerce platforms to sell their product-

Table 6: Table showing usage of E-commerce platform by the respondents

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	yes	31	50.8%	51.7%	51.7%
	no	29	47.5%	48.3%	100.0%
Missing	.	1	1.6%		
Total		61	100.0%		

Source: Made through PSPP

Chart 6 : Chart showing use of E-commerce platforms

Source: Made through excel

Interpretation-

This question provided the usage of E-commerce platforms by the respondents. This ecommerce platforms included use of amazon, Flipkart and other websites to sell the products of their business. Nearly 51% of the respondents ticked ‘yes’ and remaining 49% ticked ‘no’ as the answer for this question.

Use of social media for their personal use-

Table 7: Table showing use of social media platforms

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid yes	53	88.3%	88.3%	88.3%
no	7	11.7%	11.7%	100.0%
Total	60	100.0%		

Source: Made through PSPP

Chart 7: Use of social media by the respondents for personal use

Source: Made through excel

Interpretation-

This chart provides the use of social media by the small business owners. Nearly 88% of the respondents use social media for personal use and only 12% of the respondents don't use social media. So we can say that it is opportunity for the owners, who use social media, to enter into social media marketing to promote their products.

Opinion of the respondents about the digitalization of small business (is it helpful in growing their business)

Table 8: Table showing the opinion of the respondents

	Frequency	percentage	Valid percentage	Cumulative percentage
Valid YES	40	66.7%	66.7%	66.7%
NO	20	33.3%	33.3%	100,0%
total	60	100.0%		

Source: Made through PSPP

Chart 8: Chart showing opinion of small business owners regarding digitalization.

Source: Made through excel

Interpretation-

This chart provides the opinion of small business owners regarding digitalization in growth of small business. Nearly 68% of the respondents believed that digitalization is helpful in growth of the business and the remaining 32% believed that it is not useful.

Opinion of the respondents whether digitalization is essential

Table 9: Table showing the opinion of the respondents

	Frequency	percentage	Valid percentage	Cumulative percentage
Valid YES	48	80.0%	80.0%	80.0%
NO	12	20.0%	20.0%	100,0%
total	60	100.0%		

Source: Made through PSPP

Chart 9: Chart showing the opinion of the respondents whether the digitalization is important or not

Source: Made through excel

Interpretation-

This chart provides the opinion of small business owners regarding whether digitalization is truly helpful in business growth. 80% of the respondents believed that digitalization is important for business growth. Only 20% responded that it is not important. It may be because they believe that they can make more profit by using traditional methods of business.

9.HYPOTHESIS:

Hypothesis 1: To study the relation between education qualification and digitalization adaption

H0: There is no relation between education qualification and digitization adaption

H1: There is relation between education qualification and digitization adaption

Hypothesis 2: To study the relation between location of the business and digitalization adaption

H0: There is no relation between education qualification and digitization adaptation

H1: There is relation between education qualification and digitization adaptation

Hypothesis testing

Hypothesis 1: To study the relation between education qualification and use of digitalization

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Sig. (2-tailed)
Pearson Chi-Square	15.69	3	.001
Likelihood Ratio	19.42	3	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	11.62	1	.001
N of Valid Cases	60		

Source: Made through PSPP

Interpretation-

In this table we can conclude that the value of 'p' in chi-square test is less than that of 0.05 the null hypotheses is rejected. So, there is relation between educational qualification and the use of digital payment platform. By this table we can conclude that there is relation between digitalization and educational qualification.

Hypothesis 2: To study the relation between area of operation and digitalization adaption

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Sig. (2-tailed)
Pearson Chi-Square	21.43	2	.000
Likelihood Ratio	28.58	2	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	17.42	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	60		

Source: Made through PSPP

Interpretation-

In this test also we can see that the calculated value is less than the significance level of 0.05. So, we reject null hypothesis. There is relation between usage of digital tools and location of the business. The digitalization is adapted more in urban areas compared to rural areas.

10. FINDINGS, SUGGESTIONS AND CONCLUSION:**Findings-**

- It was found that there is a relationship between educational qualification of small business owners and digital adaptation
- It was also found that the area or location as well as use of digital tools were also dependent
- Small business owners believed that digitalization is helpful in their business growth. Nearly 67% of the respondents approved that it is important in growth.
- Small business owners believes that digitalization is useful in growing their business. It helps them in reaching a wider market
- Nearly 80% of the respondents stated that digitalization of small business is essential in growth of the country

Suggestions-

- Use of digital platforms such as e-commerce platforms, social media platforms will help the company in dealing with wide market.
- Digitalization will help small business to stay in the market and also to compete with big giant companies.
- Use of social media also helps in using some innovation in manufacturing activities.
- It helps small business to perform marketing and promotional activities at very less cost.
- Digitalization also helps to maintain good relation customers by storing customer information in company database.

Conclusion-

The study focused on socio-economic condition of the small business owners. We also studied the challenges faced by small business especially after government focused on digitalization. However, the digitalization of small business will help small business by

increasing the revenue, cutting down marketing cost and also helps in improving their competitiveness.

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